

Exploring NIH R01 success by Mentored K awardees

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Introduction

Nurturing the biomedical research workforce is central to the NIH mission. Since 1998, NIH has invested over \$3B in its flagship Career Development (K) Awards program¹, to help postdoctoral researchers transition to “research independence”, i.e., to become Principal Investigators on R01 or equivalent grants (R01-Eq)². The bulk of funding (~\$1.8B) goes to Individual Mentored Career Development Awards (MKs)³. MK awardees achieve independence at higher rates than non-MK peers, yet 50% or fewer ever obtain an R01-Eq^{4,5}. Here we evaluate success of MK awardees securing their first R01-Eq; examining whether MK award type or cohort alters chances of success. Using time-to-event models we explore group censoring, changes in event (“hazard”) rates over time, and differential “frailty” to gain insights.

Methods

Data collection

8,879 MK awardees (K01, K08, K23) with award dates 1999 to 2013 were extracted from NIH RePORTER. We determined whether each PI had received an R01-Eq award through 2020. If so, year of R01-Eq was recorded. Those with no R01-Eq were censored at the final year of observation.

Statistical analysis

To evaluate trends over time we used five, 3-year cohorts (1999-2001, 2002-2004, etc.). For each cohort representation and success rate of each MK award type was tabulated. Survival models⁶ were used to determine if there were systematic differences in rate of achieving research independence by MK type. Model-estimated time from MK award to R01-Eq award was summarized by MK type and MK cohort. Stratified Kaplan-Meier curves were generated, and log-rank tests used to detect significant difference in the

cumulative probability of R01-Eq success across MK type. Differences by MK cohort were examined using a similar approach⁷. Non-, semi-, and fully parametric modelling approaches including Cox proportional hazard (CPH) and frailty models⁷ were used to estimate coefficients associated with the main effects of MK type (Model 1), MK cohort (Model 2), and MK type x MK cohort interaction (Model 3). Frailty models with a range of baseline hazard distributions (exponential, Weibull, log-logistic) and frailty (gamma, inverse Gaussian) assumptions were compared using Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) to identify parameters with the best model fit. Success rates from complimentary models were visualized using smoothed hazard functions.

Results

Overall, R01-Eq success rate was 47.3%. K08s had the highest success rate in four of the five cohorts (Table 1). Among the successful, median time from MK to R01-Eq was 5 years (interquartile range: 4, 7).

Table 1. R01 or equivalent funding success of MK award types within three-year cohorts

	N	K01	K08	K23
Overall	8879	45.5%	49.5%	46.2%
1999-01	1611	46%	50%	48%
2002-04	2035	47%	46%	47%
2005-07	1868	46%	49%	46%
2008-10	1838	46%	52%	43%
2011-13	1527	42%	53%	48%

Figure 1. Kaplan-Meier survival curves of time until R01 or equivalent success from MK award, stratified by MK award type (1A) and cohort (1B)

Log-rank omnibus testing⁸ revealed that time-to-R01-Eq survival curves differed significantly between the MK award types ($p = 0.01$) and cohorts ($p < .001$) (Fig 1). A log-logistic model with gamma frailty was the best parametric model (lowest AIC). Table 2 displays results of CPH and frailty regression for the three models. The CPH model found a significantly higher rate of R01-Eq success for K08 vs K01 awardees (Model 1). CPH and frailty models showed higher success rates for MK awardees in the most recent vs earliest cohort. No significant differences for MK type, MK cohort or their interaction were found for Model 3. Hazard function visualizations for Models 1 and 2 are shown in Figure 2. The highest probability of success occurs within the first 6 years after MK award for all strata.

Discussion

Our results are an important first step in exploring what factors may be influencing success of early-career investigators who have MK awards. We explored two hypotheses for variation in research independence among MK awardees: cohort effects and MK type. Success of K08 versus K01 awardees differed with CPH models but significance vanished once cohort was adjusted for. Similarly, unadjusted rates of success were higher for awardees in the most recent cohort, but not when adjustment was added in Model 3. This initial work cannot explain the mechanism in R01-Eq funding success and argues for deeper exploration.

	Coefficient					
	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
	CPH	Frailty	CPH	Frailty	CPH	Frailty
MK Type						
K08	0.10*	0.12	-	-	0.11	0.11
K23	0.01	-0.13	-	-	0.06	-0.02
Cohort						
2: 2002-04	-	-	-0.03	-0.07	0.06	0.14
3: 2005-07	-	-	0.02	0.12	0.07	0.25
4: 2008-10	-	-	0.06	0.02	0.09	-0.06
5: 2011-13	-	-	0.21*	0.22*	0.13	0.19
Interaction						
K08 x 2	-	-	-	-	-0.15	-0.33
K23 x 2	-	-	-	-	-0.09	-0.24
K08 x 3	-	-	-	-	-0.02	-0.04
K23 x 3	-	-	-	-	-0.10	-0.35
K08 x 4	-	-	-	-	0.06	0.27
K23 x 4	-	-	-	-	-0.14	-0.09
K08 x 5	-	-	-	-	0.18	0.14
K23 x 5	-	-	-	-	0.10	0.0
Theta	-	4.39*	-	4.45*	-	4.51*
AIC	73546	31786	73534	31840	73530	31910

* $p < 0.05$, Reference groups: K01, Cohort 1 (1999-01), K01 x Cohort 1

Table 2. Survival analysis of time until R01 or equivalent success from MK award (N = 8,879)

Figure 2. Smoothed hazard functions based on CPH models of time until R01 or equivalent success from MK award, stratified by MK award type (2A) and cohort (2B)

Significant frailty terms in our parametric models signal that there are confounders not included in the time-to-event model that may explain the heterogeneity in outcomes⁹. Limitations of the current work includes lack of other variables to aid in describing the cohorts. To address this, we are linking data (ex. Number publications, area of research) to individual awardees including latent variables representing social capital that may be associated with R01-Eq success. These additional factors may partially explain some of the variance in outcome currently accounted for using frailty terms. We are in the process of investigating the effect of various characteristics of MK awardee and their co-authors as graph-based predictors of MK to R01-equivalent success¹⁰. This work will elucidate the evolution of author's prestige over time and its role in the Matthew Mechanism.¹¹

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